

A comparative study of system-level PMSM models with either current or flux-linkage state variables used for vibro-acoustic computation

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Abstract—This paper explores different high-fidelity, system-level models for permanent magnet synchronous machines. The main attributes examined are electromagnetic torque and forces representing the main contribution sources for noise and vibration in electrical powertrains. First, two types of electromagnetic models extracted from finite element analysis are presented: the current and flux-linkage state variable models. Afterwards, two force transformation models used for system-level vibro-acoustic computation are explored and a spectral convergence test is proposed. Procedures regarding model implementation, such as look-up table derivation/inversion are discussed and design trade-offs are analyzed. Finally, the different model results are benchmarked against a finite element model and the real-time performance is presented.

Index Terms—PMSM, system-level model, force model, magnetic co-energy, look-up table inversion;

I. INTRODUCTION

The permanent magnet synchronous machine (PMSM) is widely used in various industrial applications and holds the position of market leader in specific segments, such as both traction and auxiliary drives in automotive applications. Decreasing time-to-market and growing product design iterations necessitate multi-attribute and multi-physics, early-design stage system-level assessments of the electric drive [1], [2].

In order to simulate noise, vibration and harshness (NVH) behavior, the control algorithms, power electronics, structural and multibody dynamics of the electric drive-train have to be simultaneously taken into account together with the PMSM model. Because this type of multi-physics coupling is time-consuming at the early design stage, a series of time-domain component models are constructed using multi-domain FE reduction techniques. Afterwards, the components are integrated in a model-based system engineering (MBSE) environment where high-fidelity, reduced-time NVH simulation scenarios are performed, as exemplified in Figure 1. The focus on this paper is kept on the time-domain electromagnetic modeling of the electrical machine including air-gap forces, using data acquired from FE analysis as described in Section II (highlighted with a dashed line in Figure 1).

Several time-domain high-fidelity PMSM models that can capture saturation and slotting effects exist and can be broadly categorized into current state variable models (CSVMs) and

flux-linkage state variable models (FSVMs). Section III explores two types of CSVMs based on magnetic co-energy [3], [4] and based on flux-linkages [5], [6] and electromagnetic torque [7] data obtained from FE. Section IV explores two types of FSVMs [8], where the difference resides in the flux-linkage map inversion technique. For an accurate time-domain NVH simulation, two main attributes are important in the voltage-fed PMSM model: the electromagnetic torque because it represents one of the main sources of the structure-born noise together with the unbalanced magnetic pull (UMP) [9] and the computed currents that represent inputs to the force models, representing the main source of the air-born noise [1]. Section V present two force transformations that are compatible with system-level design: the lumped tooth force (LTF) with multiple divisions per tooth and the spatially decomposed force (SDF) transformation. A spectral convergence test is proposed in order to ensure the spectral accuracy of the force transformation models.

II. PMSM TIME-DOMAIN MODELING

A. General machine equations

The generic phase voltage equation of a PMSM is expressed as:

$$v = Ri + \frac{d\phi}{dt}, \text{ with } \phi = f_i(i, \vartheta_e), \quad (1)$$

where ϕ , v , i , ϑ_e and R are the machine flux linkage, voltage, current, electrical angle and phase resistance, and represents the CSVM. In order to perform a change of state variables from current to flux-linkage and ensure the integrability of (1), a bijective relationship between the current i and the flux-linkage ϕ should exist for all angle positions: ϑ_e :

$$\phi = f_i(i, \vartheta_e) \xleftrightarrow{\text{bijectivity}} i = f_\phi(\phi, \vartheta_e).$$

By neglecting the losses in the coupling field (thus considering a conservative field) the bijectivity assumption holds and the FSVM voltage equation:

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = v - Ri, \text{ with } i = f_\phi(\phi, \vartheta_e) \quad (2)$$

can be used [10].

Fig. 1. Overview of the PMSM drive system-level modeling used for NVH simulation

B. Extracting LUT data from a series of magnetostatic FE analysis

The simulations are conducted on a 8-pole, 48-slots, V-shaped Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (IPMSM) with the parameters detailed in Table I and geometry presented in Figure 2(a).

TABLE I
SIMULATED IPMSM PARAMETERS

Parameter	unit	value
Peak torque	Nm	207
Base rotational speed	rpm	3,000
Stator outer diameter	mm	264
Stator stack length	mm	50.8
Air gap length	mm	0.73

In order to construct the electromagnetic system-level PMSM model, a series of magnetostatic Finite Element (FE) computations that sweep through the current and rotor position range are performed offline. The computed data (magnetic co-energy, flux-linkages, electromagnetic torque, air-gap flux density) together with the current and position brake-points are stored in nD look-up tables (LUTs), where n represents the table dimension, as shown in Figure 2(b). For increasing computational speed, PMSM phase-belt symmetry can be taken into account when the sweep analysis is performed. Also, the $dq0$ reference frame can be used [3], where a smart choice of the dq current break-points grid can be selected [11]. Accuracy can also be improved by up-sampling an integer factor the LUT data $f(i_{min} : \Delta i : i_{max}, \vartheta_e) \xrightarrow{\text{upsampled}}$

Fig. 2. Cross-section of IPMSM (a), raw (b) and upsampled (c) magnetic co-energy LUT at $\vartheta_m = 0$.

$f(i_{min} : \frac{\Delta i}{k} : i_{max}, \vartheta_e)$, where k is the integer factor, followed by interpolation.

III. PMSM CURRENT STATE VARIABLE MODEL

The equations of the CSVM are based on the magnetic co-energy, currents, flux-linkages and differential inductances. Figure 3 exemplifies these quantities on a saturated B-H curve.

Fig. 3. Magnetic energy/co-energy and incremental/differential inductance.

A. Description of the CSVM

The governing equations for the CSVM in the dq reference frame (the zero sequence current will be ignored from here on) are obtained by applying the Park transformation to (1), where i_{dq} , v_{dq} , ϕ_{dq} are the direct and quadrature components of the phase current, voltage and flux-linkage, ω_e is synchronous electrical speed, ϑ_m is the machine mechanical angle, p is the pole-pair number, T_{em} is the electromagnetic torque and W_c is the magnetic co-energy. The electromagnetic torque can be decomposed as the sum of the electric input source torque ($T_{el} = p \frac{3}{2} (i_q \phi_d - i_d \phi_q)$) and an alternating ripple torque caused by the slotting effect, called here the fluctuating torque component ($T_{mag} = \frac{\partial W_c}{\partial \vartheta_m}$) [3], [1]:

$$v_d = R i_d + \frac{d\phi_d(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e)}{dt} - \omega_e \phi_q(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e) \text{ and} \quad (3)$$

$$v_q = R i_q + \frac{d\phi_q(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e)}{dt} + \omega_e \phi_d(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e), \quad (3)$$

$$T_{em} = \frac{p}{2} (i_q \phi_d(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e) - i_d \phi_q(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e)) + \frac{\partial W_c(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_m)}{\partial \vartheta_m}. \quad (4)$$

By applying the chain rule to the flux-linkages in (3) and rearranging into the standard form (the function arguments (i_d, i_q, ϑ_e) are suppressed for simplicity), the voltage equation can be solved numerically during run-time (eg. using Gaussian elimination followed by back substitution):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_d}{dt} &= \frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial i_d} \frac{d\phi_d}{dt} - \omega_e \phi_q \\ \frac{di_q}{dt} &= \frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_q} \frac{d\phi_q}{dt} + \omega_e \phi_d \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_d &= R i_d + \frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial i_d} \frac{di_d}{dt} - \omega_e \phi_q \\ v_q &= R i_q + \frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_q} \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_e \phi_d \end{aligned}$$

It is important to note that because the derivatives are obtained from LUTs that are computed prior to launching the simulation, numerical differentiation is avoided during simulation run-time. The cause of inaccuracy in the CSVM are numerical errors given by the first and second order differentiation occurring in the pre-processing stage, that can be reduced with proper interpolation and differentiation techniques, and the possible error in the numerical solver related to the differential matrix inversion during run-time (5).

Fig. 4. Elements of the differential inductance matrix (a-c) [H], torque ripple coefficients (d,e) [V · s/rad] and the fluctuating torque component (f) [Nm] at $\vartheta_e = 0$ used in the CSVM and obtained from flux-linkage model (blue) and magnetic co-energy model (red).

B. CSVM using magnetic co-energy data

All the model variables, such as flux-linkages, the fluctuating torque component, and the differential inductance matrix is obtained by differentiating (first and second order) the machine magnetic co-energy ($W_c(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_e)$) with respect to current and position [3]: $T_{mag} = \frac{\partial W_c}{\partial \vartheta_m}$, $\phi_d = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial W_c}{\partial i_d}$, $\phi_q = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial W_c}{\partial i_q}$. $\frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial i_d} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial^2 W_c}{\partial i_d^2}$, $\frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_q} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial^2 W_c}{\partial i_q^2}$, $\frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_d} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial^2 W_c}{\partial i_d \partial i_q}$, $\frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial \vartheta_e} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial^2 W_c}{\partial i_d \partial \vartheta_e}$, $\frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial \vartheta_e} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial^2 W_c}{\partial i_q \partial \vartheta_e}$. The differentiation is usually performed numerically and can be executed prior to simulation start and storing the results in LUTs [2] as depicted in Figure 4. In order to compute the first order and second order derivative, the co-energy 3D LUT $W_c(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_m)$ is cubic spline interpolated [4].

C. CSVM using flux-linkages and torque data

The second CSVM uses the flux-linkages extracted directly from the magnetostatic FE analysis while the differential inductance matrix elements are obtained through first-order differentiation of the flux-linkage. Because co-energy is not used in this model, the fluctuating torque component (T_{mag})

from equation (4) cannot be computed, thus the electromagnetic torque is extracted directly from the FE simulation and stored in a 3D LUT:

$$T_{em} = T_{LUT}(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_m). \quad (6)$$

The flux-linkages and LUT torque CSVM model is less insensitive to FE mesh noise because only first-order derivatives are necessary for model implementation.

IV. PMSM FLUX-LINKAGE STATE VARIABLE MODEL

A. Description of the FSVM

The governing equations of the FSVM, again in the dq reference frame, are obtained by integrating and applying the Park transformation to (2):

$$\int \phi_d = (v_d - Ri_d(\phi_d, \phi_q, \vartheta_e) + \omega_e \phi_q) dt \quad \text{and} \quad (7)$$

$$\int \phi_q = (v_q - Ri_q(\phi_d, \phi_q, \vartheta_e) - \omega_e \phi_d) dt$$

while the electromagnetic torque is extracted directly from the FE simulation as in (6). Figure 5 presents the block diagram for the CSVM and FSVM voltage equations. In the FSVM,

Fig. 5. Block diagrams for the CSVM and FSVM dq voltage equations

the causes of inaccuracy are errors given by the inversion of non-linear flux-linkages tables. Different methods exist for this procedure [12], [13]. In this paper, a surface fitting method and a polynomial Taylor series expansion method are used and the results compared in terms of execution time and accuracy. One advantage of the FSVM is that the current can be decomposed into Fourier series that take into account the most important harmonics, thus a harmonic analysis can be executed at the system-level (eg. current harmonic injection) [1], [14].

B. Inverting flux-linkage LUTs based on polynomial surface fitting

The first LUT inversion method uses surface fitting of the flux-linkage scattered data ($\phi = f(i, \vartheta_e)$) to a regular spaced grid of dq currents as shown in Figure 6. This surface fitting method uses bicubic interpolation and gives an option of changing the surface linearity (smoothness) by modifying the second-order derivatives with a scaling factor [15].

Fig. 6. λ_{dq} LUTs (a,b) and i_{dq} LUTs using the surface fitting inversion method (b,c) in the FSVM at $\vartheta_m = 0$.

C. Inverting flux-linkage LUTs based on the Taylor series expansion

At a certain rotor position for a set of dq axis currents (\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q), the dq axis flux-linkages ($\tilde{\phi}_d, \tilde{\phi}_q$) can be computed. A Taylor series of $\phi_d(i_d, i_q)$ and $\phi_q(i_d, i_q)$ in the vicinity of (\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_d |_{\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q}(i_d, i_q) &= \phi_d(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q) + \frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial i_d}(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q)(i_d - \tilde{i}_d) + \\ &\frac{\partial \phi_d}{\partial i_q}(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q)(i_q - \tilde{i}_q) + o(i_d - \tilde{i}_d) + o(i_q - \tilde{i}_q), \\ \phi_q |_{\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q}(i_d, i_q) &= \phi_q(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q) + \frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_d}(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q)(i_d - \tilde{i}_d) + \\ &\frac{\partial \phi_q}{\partial i_q}(\tilde{i}_d, \tilde{i}_q)(i_q - \tilde{i}_q) + o(i_d - \tilde{i}_d) + o(i_q - \tilde{i}_q), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $i_d - \tilde{i}_d = \Delta i_d$ and $i_q - \tilde{i}_q = \Delta i_q$ are the current errors and $\tilde{\phi}_d - \phi_d^* = \Delta \phi_d$ and $\tilde{\phi}_q - \phi_q^* = \Delta \phi_q$ are the flux linkages errors obtained from the flux-linkages set-points ϕ_d^*, ϕ_q^* . The solution is found by setting $o(i_d - \tilde{i}_d) = 0$ and $o(i_q - \tilde{i}_q) = 0$ and solving the following system of linear equations giving a linear extrapolation of the flux-linkages (that requires inverting the differential inductance matrix):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta i_d \\ \Delta i_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_d}{\partial i_d} & \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_d}{\partial i_q} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_q}{\partial i_d} & \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_q}{\partial i_q} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \phi_d \\ \Delta \phi_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

D. Comparison between the two LUT inversion methods

The accuracy of the two proposed inversion methods is analyzed using the following procedure: a set of reference dq currents is fed to the dq flux-linkages LUTs and the resulting flux-linkages are next fed to the dq currents LUTs ($i^* \rightarrow$

$f_\phi(i, \vartheta_e) \xrightarrow{\text{output}} \tilde{\phi} \xrightarrow{\text{input}} f_i(\phi, \vartheta_e) \xrightarrow{\text{output}} \tilde{i}$). The absolute current error is afterwards computed: $i_{err} = |i^* - \tilde{i}|$ and results

Fig. 7. i_d and i_q absolute current error for the Taylor series (a,b) and Surface Fitting (c,d) LUTs inversion methods at $\vartheta_m = 0$.

are presented in Figure 7. The Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) for the depicted current range are: $MAE, i_d = 0.5056$ [A] and $MAE, i_q = 0.3110$ [A] for the Surface Fitting method and $MAE, i_d = 0.0991$ [A] and $MAE, i_q = 0.0525$ [A] for the Taylor series method. Although there is one order of magnitude difference between the two methods error, they are relatively small in value compared to the set-point currents. Also, the computation time of the two methods differ, where the Taylor series is more computational expensive.

V. ELECTRICAL MACHINE AIR-GAP FORCE MODELS

Several numerical methods for computing air-gap magnetic forces from FE analysis exist (both for global and local forces), such as the Nodal Forces, Surface Force Density and the Maxwell Stress Tensor (MST) method [16]. In this paper two force transformations are compared and used in the system-level model: the SDF and the LTF obtained from the MST applied in the air-gap. This selection is driven by the time-domain structural models that are coupled with each respective force model (as shown in Figure 1): the SDF is used in the vibration synthesis method [17] and the LTF is used with a reduced-order structural dynamic model, both in the state-space representation. The results for both techniques are stored in LUTs that are current and position dependent $f(i_d, i_q, \vartheta_m)$, where in the case of LTF method each division/tooth has assigned a force value, while in the SDF model each force shape coefficient is stored independently.

A. Spatially decomposed force

The force wave is distributed in the air-gap space (α) and is dependent on rotor position or time (t), thus it is possible to

Fig. 8. Force shape decomposition and superposition.

apply a 2D Fourier series decomposition along the mentioned dimensions using the $\cos - \sin$ orthogonal basis:

$$F_{sup}(t, \alpha) = \sum_{m=0}^M f_m(t, \alpha) = f_0(t) + \sum_{m=1}^M (f_{cos,m}(t)\cos(m\alpha) + f_{sin,m}(t)\sin(m\alpha)) \quad (10)$$

where M is the total number of spatial harmonics considered, m represents the spatial force order (truncation is applied by taking into account the important spatial orders), and $f_{cos,m}$ and $f_{sin,m}$ represent the temporal-dependent amplitude factors. The SDF is shown in Figure 8, where the superposition of principal excitation shapes (red) and each independent force shape (blue) is showed for one operating point at a fixed rotor position.

B. Lumped tooth force

In this transformation the force wave is integrated (lumped) over a fixed number of tooth arc length divisions ($\Delta\alpha$):

$$F_{lumped}(t, \alpha) = \int_{\alpha}^{\alpha + \Delta\alpha} F(t, \alpha) d\alpha. \quad (11)$$

The procedure is visually shown in Figure 9(a) where the tooth nodal force is lumped using 2 and 4 divisions in the radial direction. Figure 9(b) shows the original force wave and the lumped tooth transformation for several $\Delta\alpha$ values in the radial direction.

C. Spectral convergence of the transformation methods

Figure 10 shows the result of a 2D Fourier transform applied to the SDF and LTF that allows to identify the most important spatial and temporal force harmonics. One limitation of the LTF for low number of total divisions is that according to the Nyquist sampling theorem the maximum observed spatial mode is limited by the total number of divisions divided by 2 (the spatial aliasing effect). Also, different numbers of divisions per tooth affect the spectral accuracy of the transformed force, thus a spectral convergence test is needed in order to select the number of tooth divisions. Figure 11 depicts the results of such an analysis where the relative amplitude (log scale) error of the main spatial orders ($-48 : 8 : 48$) with their respective temporal frequencies are computed for the different transformation models, where the benchmark is the original

Fig. 9. Graphical representation of the LTF transformation (a) and LTF shape with multiple divisions/tooth (b).

Fig. 10. Temporal (1:30) and spatial (-48:8:48) force harmonics for SDF (a) and LTF with different numbers of $\Delta\alpha$ (b-d).

force shape. This analysis shows that the SDF model has low errors compared to the LTF with 1 division/tooth where only the -8,0 and 8 spatial orders are accurate.

VI. RESULTS

A. Comparison of different EM system-level models and the FE model

In Figure 12 the electromagnetic torque and line-to-line phase voltage for the different methods are compared at steady-state in time and frequency domain, while Figure (13) shows torque results for run-up operation. The benchmark

Fig. 11. Temporal (1:30) and spatial (-48:8:48) harmonics relative error for SDF (a) and LTF with different numbers of $\Delta\alpha$ (b-d).

torque (T_{FE}) is obtained from refined (small angle steps) FE simulation. This implies that the difference between the benchmark torque and the one stored in LUT (T_{LUT}) is caused by the interpolation.

B. Comparison between different system-level force models

Steady-state time domain results for the SDF and LTF transformation models for one operating point are shown in Figure 14, while run-up results in the frequency domain are showed in Figure 15. The LTF contains all significant time orders (8, 16, 24, 32, 40, 48...), while the SDF contains time orders specific for each independent force shape.

C. Real-time performance

The real-time performance of the CSVM and FSVM is analyzed by performing a frequency analysis of the two systems during run-up operation using a variable-step solver. System linearization is performed at each time instance and the highest frequencies are saved. Figure 16 shows the instantaneous and global maximum frequencies (eigenfrequencies) for each model, while the boundary values for the fixed-step simulation with Explicit Euler solver that will match in results with the variable-step solver are: $\Delta t = 1.65 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [s] for the CSVM and $\Delta t = 1.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [s] for the FSVM.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper different high-fidelity, time-domain PMSM models obtained from magnetic FE analysis are presented and compared. For the voltage and torque equations, two types of models are discussed: the CSVM and FSVM. Results showed that the flux-linkage CSVM and FSVMs are very similar compared to the FEA model, where the CSVM has a more

(a) Time-domain electromagnetic torque waveform

(b) FFT spectra of electromagnetic torque

(c) Time-domain phase voltage waveform

(d) FFT spectra of phase voltage

Fig. 12. Steady-state torque and voltage results for $i_d = -20$ and $i_q = 60$

natural implementation because there is no need for LUT inversion - the model parameters can be extracted directly from the FEA. The FSVMs are useful when a current harmonic model is used (in conjuncture with the co-energy torque formulation). Although the co-energy CSVm ensures the energy preservation criteria (assuming zero coupling field losses) it is more sensitive to mesh noise that amplifies computation errors of first and second-order derivatives LUTs. Because no derivatives are computed during simulation run-time, both models have similar frequency-domain characteristics with respect to the numerical solver (real-time performance).

(a) Torque spectrogram for the FE model

(b) Torque spectrogram for the CSVm co-energy model

(c) 48th and 24th torque orders comparison

Fig. 13. Run-up torque results using constant current input

Fig. 14. Time-domain force models.

For the radial forces two transformation models are discussed: the SDF and LTF approach. The force transformation methods are linked with the time-domain structural dynamics model that are coupled to. This paper shows the importance of a spectral convergence test for the LTF in order to determine the minimum number of divisions per tooth.

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Fig. 15. Run-up torque results using constant current input

Fig. 16. CSVM/FSVM frequency analysis.

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